

Sustainable Energy in ICT Industry: Supplying Mobile Networks with RES

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The Information and Communication Technology (ICT) industry has a key role in the today's information and knowledge society. Its main scope is the integration of telecommunications, computers and all the necessary software, hardware, storage, and audio-visual systems, which enable users to access, store, transmit, and manipulate information. Recent studies reveal astonishing figures on how ICT industry is becoming a major component of the energy consumption budget. Detailed surveys show that ICT is responsible for approximately 4% of world energy consumption [1]. Also the CO₂ emissions of the ICT nowadays exceed the carbon output of the entire aviation industry [2]. Moreover, according to major industrial players, in 2020 the capacity demand of ICT will increase by a factor of 1000. Such a huge demand will bring along a considerable growth in terms of energy requirements and carbon footprint. Some projections indicate that next-generation ICT systems will require electricity in amounts that cannot be generated or transported to major metropolitan areas [3], [4].

In telecommunication networks, most of the power consumption comes from wireless and fixed access networks, whose equipment, while consuming less than that of core networks, exists in much larger numbers. For example, in mobile access networks, one macro base station consumes only about 1400W per hour, but altogether these devices contribute 80% of all mobile network energy consumption.

In order to meet the increasing demand of capacity, standardization bodies are working on solutions based on dense deployment of low range/capacity base stations (BSs), the so called small cells (SCs). For instance, 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), the standardization body of the mobile networks, is proposing an original architecture, the so called Heterogeneous Network (HetNet), where macro cells are supported by overlaying SCs [5] to achieve the capacity demand. HetNets also guarantee more energy efficiency due to the lower power consumption of the SCs (from 12W to 100W depending on the coverage).

This paper aims to present our two main research goals on the field:

- Definition of procedures to manage the communication when SCs are supplied with Renewable Energy Sources (RES), mainly photovoltaic plants or wind turbines. Such procedures are designed in order to have an energy self-sustainable network, able to maintain the capacity demand and, at the same time, to reduce its consumption from the energy grid.
- Design of procedures to automatically enable sleep mode in BSs, when they are not needed for providing services in order to increase the network energy efficiency.

Keywords: energy efficiency, renewable energy sources, Information and Communication Technology, mobile networks, sustainability

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